

Macro-Benthic Diversity Index of Molluscan Species in Kanher Reservoir, Satara (Maharashtra-India)

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Abstract:

Mollusca are comprised by about 120 000 species and is the second most diverse animal phylum in animal kingdom. Molluscs are found in various habitat such as freshwater, marine and terrestrial forms. These Invertebrates are inhabitants of fresh water bodies and are important component of food chain in aquatic ecosystem. The gastropods and pelecypods the bio-indicators for trophic of lotic and lentic ecosystems. The phylum mollusca have a large group of animals having varied size, shape, habits and occupy different environment. The taxonomic survey of Indian freshwater mollusca has been done by Zoological Survey of India.

Molluscans are the bioindicators aquatic ecosystem and they are suitable for biological monitoring. The gastropods and pelecypods the bio-indicators of lotic and lentic ecosystems. Water pollution influence the freshwater molluscans diversity. Mollusca are considered the most diverse and dominant benthic fauna both of lentic and lotic aquatic ecosystems. The taxonomic survey of Indian freshwater Mollusca has been done by Zoological Survey of India (Subba Rao 1989). The present study focused on assessing the macro-benthic diversity index of molluscan species in Kanher reservoir over two consecutive years, from February 2022 to January 2023 and February 2023 to January 2024.

Keywords: Mollusca, Kanher reservoir, Diversity, Ecosystem, Taxonomy etc.

Introduction:

Molluscs are found in freshwater, marine water as well as on land habitats with extremely diverse groups. They are economically, ecologically, medicinally as well as ornamentally important groups of organisms. In the world, there are 80,000 to 1,00,000 molluscan species, among them 50,000 are gastropods and 15,000 are bivalves. Molluscs serve as intermediate hosts as well as vectors for human diseases.

The measurement of Molluscan Diversity Index (MDI) is used to assess the biodiversity of molluscan species in a given area. This index is typically calculated using species richness (the total number of different species present in an

area) (Kumar, 2019). The diversity index can help us to understand the health and stability of an ecosystem, as mollusks are often good indicators of environmental conditions due to their sensitivity to changes in their surroundings (Weerakoon, 2021). The Molluscan Diversity Index involves collecting samples from an area, identifying and counting the different molluscan species present, and applying the chosen diversity index formula to the data collected. This can provide valuable insights into the ecological health and biodiversity of the area (Mirza, 2019).

Materials and Methods:

A. Study Area:

Kanher reservoir is constructed in 1986 near Kanher village of Satara district in Maharashtra, India. Which is 12 Km away from Satara city. Kanher village is spread in 530 hectares having 414 houses with 1,955 population. Kanher reservoir is medium irrigation project constructed on Venna river near Kanher village of Satara district (45° 31.85" N and 73° 52' 27.14" E) and the water storage capacity is 286 mm³.

Study Stations of Kanher Reservoir.

Station No.	Station Name	Longitude	Latitude
KS I	Shri Vardayani mata fisherie project	17° 44' 41" N	73° 54' 12" E
KS II	Ozare	17° 46' 14" N	73° 51' 21" E
KS III	Kaloshi	17° 45' 50" N	73° 50' 28" E
KS IV	Saigao	17° 43' 42" N	73° 54' 37" E

KS=Kanher Station

B. Sampling of molluscan species:

Molluscan sampling took place from Kanher reservoir in the Satara district throughout the years February 2022 to January 2023 and February 2023 to January 2024. Samples were collected using a variety of techniques, including hand picking, sieving with a sieve (pore size 0.425 mm), hand net and forceps, among others.

Specimens were collected from the mud, the stone surface, the vegetation at early in the morning. After collection, all organisms were washed and cleaned under running tap water by using sieve, excess debris and mud was removed by using brush. Absorbent tissue was used to remove excess water and moisture. The well cleaned specimens were identified by lens or microscope and their characters by using standard literature.

Identification was done by using the hand lens, Fluorescent microscope (Dexuxe), Projection microscope SP-16 and standard identification keys such as Records of the Zoological Survey of India (ZSI) and Handbook on Indian freshwater molluscs (Dey, 1992).

C. Statistical analysis:

The statistical examination of averages of molluscan diversity, involved the determination of average specimen numbers. Additionally, diversity indices like Simpson's 1-D and Shannon's H were derived using the Past 3.22 computer application software.

Results and Discussion:

The Molluscan species recorded from Kanher reservoir were carried out During the study period from February 2022 to January 2023, the number of each species were counted as *Filopaludina bengalensis* (10, 8, 11 and 10), *Bellamya bengalensis* (16, 19, 22 and 19), *Mieniplotia scabra* (14, 12, 17 and 12), *Indoplanorbis exustus* (11, 15, 10 and 5), *Melanoides tuberculata* (14, 14, 10 and 14), *Lymnaea accuminata* (15, 15, 21 and 15), *Lymnaea stagnalis* (17, 17, 19 and 17), *Radix rufescens* (13, 13, 15 and 13), *Lamellidens corrianus* (12, 9, 13 and 11), *Tarebia lineata* (14, 12, 19 and 14), *Parreysia favidens* (12, 12, 12 and 12), *Lamellidens marginalis* (17, 16, 11 and 15), *Parreysia corrugata* (14, 14, 14 and 14), *Physella acuta* (17, 17, 17 and 17), *Corbicula striatella*

(14, 14, 14 and 14) and *Corbicula regularis* (15, 15, 15 and 15) at sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III and KS IV respectively (**Table No. 2**).

During the research period of February 2023 to January 2024, the number of each molluscan species was counted as follows: *Filopaludina bengalensis* (18, 14, 13 and 14), *Bellamya bengalensis* (17, 21, 17 and 20), *Mieniplotia scabra* (16, 21, 14 and 17), *Indoplanorbis exustus* (12, 12, 16 and 14), *Melanoides tuberculata* (17, 16, 14 and 15), *Lymnaea accuminata* (21, 13, 11 and 17), *Lymnaea stagnalis* (10, 11, 19 and 13), *Radix rufescens* (10, 9, 14 and 11), *Lamellidens corrianus* (26, 21, 19 and 19), *Tarebia lineata* (15, 14, 15 and 12), *Parreysia favidens* (16, 14, 16 and 17), *Lamellidens marginalis* (15, 20, 19 and 20), *Parreysia corrugata* (19, 16, 18 and 15), *Physella acuta* (16, 12, 16 and 13), *Corbicula striatella* (16, 15, 19 and 15) and *Corbicula regularis* (17, 17, 21 and 17) at sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III and KS IV respectively (**Table No. 2**).

Molluscan species at sampling stations of Kanher reservoir for the year 2022-2023 were recorded as 225, 222, 240 and 217 at KS I, KS II, KS III and KS IV respectively (**Graph. No. 1**). The total number of insect species counted as 261, 246, 261 and 249 at sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III and KS IV respectively from Kanher reservoir (**Graph. No. 2**). During the study period, totally 1921 (one thousand nine hundred twenty one) individuals were recorded from KS I, KS II, KS III and KS IV sampling stations of Kanher reservoir.

At sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV in Kanher reservoir, the percentage composition of molluscan species was recorded as 25%, 25%, 26%, and 24% over the period of February 2022 to January 2023. The percentage composition at KS III was 26% which was seen to be high, while the percentage composition at KS

IV was 24%, which was lower in number at Kanher reservoir (**Fig. No. 1**). At sampling sites KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV in Kanher reservoir from February 2023 to January 2024, the percentage composition of molluscan species was 26%, 24%, 26%, and 24%, respectively (**Fig. No. 2**).

The Simpson_1-D diversity index of molluscan species at sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV in Dhom reservoir from February 2022 to January 2023 was 0.9362, 0.935, 0.9336 and 0.9341 respectively (**Fig. No. 3**). In Kanher reservoir from February 2022 to January 2023, the Shannon_H diversity index of molluscan species at KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV was 2.762, 2.752, 2.742 and 2.742 respectively (**Fig. No. 4**). From February 2023 to January 2024, the Simpson_1-D diversity index of molluscan species at sampling stations KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV was 0.9341, 0.934, 0.9359 and 0.9357 respectively, in Dhom reservoir (**Fig. No. 5**). While the Shannon_H diversity index of molluscan species at KS I, KS II, KS III, and KS IV were 2.746, 2.744, 2.759 and 2.758 respectively (**Fig. No. 6**).

Similar types of results were obtained by Latha *et al.* (2010). He observed 21 families of Mollusca from Kadinamkulam lakes (South Kerala-India). Cejka (2011) was observed 25 species of Mollusca (15 Gastropods and 10 Bivalvia) in small reservoirs of Malacol Bohemoslov, SW Slovakia. According to Dorlikar (2009), totally 12 species of molluscs from six orders, eight families, and ten genera with Simpson index ranged from 0.12 to 0.2 and with Shannon-Weiner index ranged from 3.3 to 3.5 were found in the Gorewada reservoir (Nagpur-India).

Kumar and Vyas (2014) reported 53 taxa of macrozoobenthic fauna in Ekruk Lake (Solapur- Maharashtra). Weerakoon *et al.* (2021) reported 11,752 molluscan specimens total, of

which 10 (96.6%) were gastropod species and 2 (3.4%) were bivalve taxa with the Shannon-Weaver diversity index ($p = 0.073$) in the reservoirs and headwater streams of the Kala Oya river basin in Sri Lanka. Sarkar *et al.* (2022) reported 5 Molluscan species with Shannon_H diversity index of 1.179, 1.144, 1.138, 1.159 and 1.175 in Gangarampur Block (Dakshin Dinajpur-West Bengal). Ramanibai and Govindan (2018) observed 34 Gastropod species and 12 Bivalvia species in Mollusc diversity at Pulicat Lagoon (India).

The diversity of mollusca depends on various factors like availability of food, temperature, pollution stress, habitat and nature of water (Filgueira *et al.*, 2013). According to Rao (1993), molluscan community play very crucial role in aquatic ecosystem by many ways like energy flow, food source, biological indicator, but nowadays their number became declined due pollution as well as human activities. According to (Lopes Lima, 2014), some species of mollusca are hosts for various diseases: *Melanoides tuberculata* is the host for nematode diseases like Paragonimiasis, Echinostomiasis and Heterophyiasis. *Indoplanorbis exustus* is the host for Cercarial Dermatitis, Echinostomiasis, Amphistomiasis nematode disease respectively.

Michael (1968) states that the diversity, richness and abundance of freshwater Mollusca recorded during the summer season, because of decomposed organic matter settled down into the bottom and such condition takes place in summer season. Number of Molluscan species get increased and proliferate in summer season has been also reported by Bath *et al.* (1999).

According to certain data of Malhotra *et al.* (1996), there is a positive link between temperature and mollusks however Shrivastava (1956) found a negative association between temperature and mollusca. According to Rosenberg *et al.*, (1993), Hardness, alkalinity, nitrate, and phosphate are some variables that positively correlate with Mollusca and are essential for their growth, survival, and proliferation. According to Hellawel, (1986), several mollusc species can tolerate in low pH (Beyond 5 pH).

During present investigation, Physico-chemical parameters play important role for growth and development of Molluscan fauna. Number of Molluscan species get increased during the summer season, because of decomposed organic matter settled down into the bottom. Mollusca perform very crucial role in functioning of aquatic ecosystems by means of food chain, energy flow, economical, bio monitoring and commercial point of view. Freshwater molluscans may survive in water with little oxygen and they serve as bioindicator of freshwater pollution since of their sedentary and sessile lifestyles.

Based on the data, it can be concluded that, Dhom reservoir demonstrated a relatively stable and diverse molluscan species community during the specified time periods. The high values of both the Simpson_1-D and Shannon_H diversity index across different sampling stations indicate a significant presence of molluscan species in the reservoir. This suggests that the habitat in the reservoir was capable of supporting a diverse range of molluscan species.

Table No. 1: Common Molluscan species occurred at study stations of Kanher reservoir during the study period February 2022 to January 2023 and February 2023 to January 2024

Sr. No.	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Species
1	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda	Thiaridae	<i>Mieniplotia scabra</i>
2	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Architaenioglossa	Uninoidae	<i>Bellamyia bengalensis</i>
3	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Architaenioglossa	Viviparidae	<i>Filopaludina bengalensis</i>
4	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Basommatophora	Lymnaeidae	<i>Radix rufescens</i>
5	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Basommatophora	Lymnaeidae	<i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i>
6	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Basommatophora	Lymnaeidae	<i>Lymnaea accuminata</i>
7	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Basommatophora	Bulinidae	<i>Indoplanorbis exustus</i>
8	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Architaenioglossa	Thiaridae	<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i>
9	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Basommatophora	Physidae	<i>Physella acuta</i>
10	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Sorbeochoncha	Tharidae	<i>Tarebia lineata</i>
11	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Unionida	Uninoidae	<i>Parreysia corrugata</i>
12	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Unionida	Viviparidae	<i>Parreysia favidens</i>
13	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Unionida	Uninoidae	<i>Lamellidens marginalis</i>
14	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Unionida	Unionidae	<i>Lamellidens corrianus</i>
15	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Cyrenidae	<i>Corbicula striatella</i>
16	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Cyrenidae	<i>Corbicula regularis</i>

Table No. 2: Molluscan species (organisms/m²) occurred at Kanher reservoir.

Sr No.	Species Name	2022-2023				2023-2024			
		KS I	KS II	KS III	KS IV	KS I	KS II	KS III	KS IV
1	<i>Filopaludina bengalensis</i>	10	8	11	10	18	14	13	14
2	<i>Bellamyia bengalensis</i>	16	19	22	19	17	21	17	20
3	<i>Mieniplotia scabra</i>	14	12	17	12	16	21	14	17
4	<i>Indoplanorbis exustus</i>	11	15	10	5	12	12	16	14
5	<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i>	14	14	10	14	17	16	14	15
6	<i>Lymnaea accuminata</i>	15	15	21	15	21	13	11	17
7	<i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i>	17	17	19	17	10	11	19	13
8	<i>Radix rufescens</i>	13	13	15	13	10	9	14	11
9	<i>Lamellidens corrianus</i>	12	9	13	11	26	21	19	19
10	<i>Tarebia lineata</i>	14	12	19	14	15	14	15	12
11	<i>Parreysia favidens</i>	12	12	12	12	16	14	16	17
12	<i>Lamellidens marginalis</i>	17	16	11	15	15	20	19	20
13	<i>Parreysia corrugata</i>	14	14	14	14	19	16	18	15
14	<i>Physella acuta</i>	17	17	17	17	16	12	16	13
15	<i>Corbicula striatella</i>	14	14	14	14	16	15	19	15
16	<i>Corbicula regularis</i>	15	15	15	15	17	17	21	17
Total species		225	222	240	217	261	246	261	249

Graph. No. 1: Molluscan species (organisms/m2) occurred at study stations of Kanher reservoir for the year 2022-2023.

Fig. No. 1: Molluscan diversity of Kanher reservoir for the year 2022-2023

Graph. No. 2: Molluscan species (organisms/m2) occurred at study stations of Kanher reservoir for the year 2023-2024

Fig. No. 2: Molluscan diversity of Kanher reservoir for the year 2023-2024

Fig. No. 3: Simpson_1-D of Molluscan species from Kanher Reservoir for the year 2022-2023

	KS I	Lower	Upper	KS II	Lower	Upper	KS III	Lower	Upper	KS IV	Lower	Upper
Simpson_1-D	0.9362	0.9277	0.9352	0.9344	0.9258	0.9344	0.9336	0.9243	0.9339	0.9341	0.9246	0.9337

Fig. 4: Shannon_H of Molluscan species from Kanher Reservoir for the year 2022-2023

	KS I	Lower	Upper	KS II	Lower	Upper	KS III	Lower	Upper	KS IV	Lower	Upper
Shannon_H	2.762	2.692	2.754	2.752	2.677	2.747	2.742	2.668	2.743	2.742	2.663	2.741

Fig. No. 5: Simpson_1-D of Molluscan species from Kanher Reservoir for the year 2023-2024

	KS I	Lower	Upper	KS II	Lower	Upper	KS III	Lower	Upper	KS IV	Lower	Upper
Simpson_1-D	0.9341	0.9254	0.9342	0.934	0.9248	0.9341	0.9359	0.9283	0.9352	0.9357	0.9276	0.935

Fig. No. 6: Shannon_H of Molluscan species from Kanher Reservoir for the year 2023-2024

	KS I	Lower	Upper	KS II	Lower	Upper	KS III	Lower	Upper	KS IV	Lower	Upper
Shannon_H	2.746	2.677	2.746	2.744	2.672	2.745	2.759	2.698	2.754	2.758	2.693	2.753

Conclusion:

The comparative study of molluscan species across four sampling stations (KS I–KS IV) in the Kanher reservoir from February 2022 to January 2024 reveals a stable, rich, and ecologically significant molluscan community.

The total population (1921 individuals) and species count trends affirm the health and biodiversity of the reservoir’s ecosystem. KS III consistently recorded higher molluscan abundance (up to 26%), suggesting favourable

local conditions, while KS IV showed slightly lower values (24%).

Diversity indices, including Simpson_1-D (0.9336–0.9362) and Shannon_H (2.742–2.762), confirm high species richness and evenness, indicating a well-balanced community without dominance by any single species. Slight inter-annual variations reflect a resilient molluscan population, capable of adapting to environmental changes. The findings highlight the ecological significance and biodiversity value of the Kanher reservoir's molluscan fauna. Continued monitoring is crucial for tracking long-term trends, detecting environmental pressures, and ensuring sustainable conservation of this aquatic ecosystem.

The diversity indices recorded for molluscan species in the Kanher reservoir across two consecutive periods (Feb 2022–Jan 2023 and Feb 2023–Jan 2024) indicate a consistently high and stable species diversity at all four sampling stations (KS I to KS IV). The Simpson_1-D index values, all above 0.93, reflect a high probability of interspecific diversity, suggesting a well-balanced molluscan community with no single species dominating. Similarly, the Shannon_H index values, ranging from approximately 2.74 to 2.76, reinforce the presence of a rich and evenly distributed molluscan population. Minor fluctuations between years suggest natural ecological variation, but overall, the reservoir maintains a healthy and diverse molluscan assemblage throughout the study period.

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